

STUDIES ON THE GELATION OF SILICIC ACID SOLS. PART III. CATIONIC AND ANIONIC EFFECTS ON THE TIME OF GELATION

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The addition of electrolytes does not bring about coagulation of silicic acid sols but lowers the time of gelation. In the region of p_H lower than that corresponding to the maximum time of gelation, the greater the valency of the cation used, the greater is the lowering of the time of gelation. At higher p_H , the effect of the valency of the cations on the gelation time becomes less and less pronounced. The behaviour with the anions is just the reverse. In each acid system the electric charge of the colloid is negative in the region of p_H beyond that corresponding to the maximum time of gelation. At lower p_H , the particles are positively charged.

It has been reported (Hurd *et al.*, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1933, 37, 321; 1934, 38, 663) that the addition of electrolytes affects the time of gelation of silicic acid sols, prepared by using acetic acid. This is perhaps not a consequence of coagulation. Some of the electrolytes are likely to influence the time of gelation mainly by altering the p_H . The time of gelation, as influenced by the addition of some electrolytes, has therefore been studied in some detail.

EXPERIMENTAL

Sols prepared by using hydrochloric acid were used. To the freshly prepared sols known quantities of electrolytes were added; the silica contents of the sols were always kept at 3.0%, but the electrolyte concentrations were varied. The p_H of the mixtures was then noted. The time of gelation of these sols was determined at 55°.

It is found that at a particular p_H , the greater the concentration of the added electrolyte, the lower is the time of gelation. Comparison of the time of gelation (t) of sols containing 2.0N concentrations of NaCl, CaCl₂ and AlCl₃ with that of the sol to which no extra amount of electrolyte has been added, is shown in Fig. 1. It appears from the curves that although the p_H corresponding to the maximum time for gelation is not appreciably affected, the value of this time is considerably lowered. Thus 2.0 N concentrations of AlCl₃, CaCl₂ and NaCl have reduced the maximum time of gelation by about 63%, 52% and 31% respectively. At about p_H 1.8 and upwards, the effect of all the three electrolytes is of the same order. Thus at p_H 2.0, concentrations (2.0 N) of the electrolytes reduce the time of gelation by about 60%. The specific effect of the added electrolytes becomes more pronounced at lower p_H . Thus, the concentrations of AlCl₃, CaCl₂ and NaCl at 2.0 N level reduce the time of gelation by about 52%, 40% and 10% respectively at 0.5 p_H , 55%, 47% and 21% respectively at 0.8 p_H , and 60%, 51% and 30% respectively at 1.0 p_H . It can therefore be concluded from the curves that the cations of higher valence reduce the time of gelation to a greater extent in the region of lower

p_H , but this effect becomes progressively less as the p_H increases. It also appears from experimental data that the specific effects of Ba^{++} and Ca^{++} ions are almost of the same order.

The influence of anions on the time of gelation may be observed by comparing the experimental data obtained with hydrochloric and sulphuric acid systems. The graphical representation of the data in Fig. 2 clearly illustrates the anion effect. At p_H lower than that corresponding to the maximum time of gelation, the effect of the valency of the anions is negligible, whereas at a higher p_H a marked anion effect is noticeable. These observations are just the reverse of what has been found in the case of the cations.

Electric Charge.—The anion and the cation effects described above naturally bring in the question of electrical charge on the particles of silicic acid. Measurements of the electrical charge have therefore been made by the electroendosmotic method used by Mukherjee (*Nature*, 1922, 110, 732) and Ghosh (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1926, 2609; 1927, 1250). Sometimes after gelation, when syneresis had started, the gel mixture was centrifuged. The lower part of the U-tube was then filled with the centrifuged gel which formed the diaphragm. The upper part of the U-tube and the side tubes were then filled with the supernatant liquid. The movement of the air bubble in the horizontal bent tube connecting the side tubes was noted. If the air bubble moves to the negative electrode, the colloid is positively charged and *vice versa*. It is found that in each acid system, the electrical charge of the colloid is negative in the region of p_H beyond that corresponding to the maximum time of gelation. At lower p_H region the particles are positively charged. Near about the maximum time of gelation, it is likely that the particles possess no charge at all or they are only slightly charged.

If the cation and the anion effects are the results of either adsorption or coagulation, the differentiation between the cations would have been prominent in the negative region and that between the anions in the positive region. The experimental facts, however, are contrary to this expectation. Moreover, the maximum time of gelation, which signifies greater stability of the sol, occurs at or near about a point where the electrical charge of the particles is perhaps zero. Adsorption or coagulation appears therefore to play a secondary role, if any, in the process of gelation of silicic acid sols.